

TRACE THEORY FOR GFRP – MIXING TSAI’S MODULUS, ASYMPTOTIC HOMOGENIZATION AND MACHINE LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

Uncertainties related to fibers and matrix properties are a drawback for engineering application of micromechanical models. To deal with this issue, Tsai’s modulus was proposed for CFRP, where the lamina elastic properties are defined in a normalized relation with the trace of stiffness matrix. An extension of this theory is proposed for GFRP following the procedure: i) laminae properties are generated using the asymptotic homogenization; ii) decision trees algorithm is applied to obtain the normalized properties according to the trace; iii) a linear relation is fit for each property. Average errors smaller than 12% are obtained comparing with experimental data.

KEYWORDS

Trace theory; asymptotic homogenization; decision trees; effective properties.

INTRODUCTION

Design composite structures is a multiscale task, becoming a challenge involving many variables (Vignoli & Savi, 2018). The first step for structural analysis is to obtain the macromechanical elastic properties, which can be done using micromechanical approaches or experimentally. An experimental program expends a long time and is associated with high costs, becoming prohibitive for optimization procedures. Hence, the micromechanical modeling is a very useful tool for engineering applications.

The main idea of micromechanics is that the effective macromechanical properties can be computed using just the constituents’ properties. The focus of this study is unidirectional lamina. For this class of composite material, many micromechanical models have been proposed in the literature with good recent advances, as reviewed by Vignoli et al. (2019) and Vignoli et al. (2022a). Among these models, the asymptotic homogenization deserves a highlight due to its solid mathematical and mechanical foundations (Kalamkarov, 1992), as well as good agreement with experimental data (Vignoli et al., 2019).

However, the weaknesses of this approach are the uncertainties related to the fiber properties, since transversal properties and Poisson’s ratios measurements are very questionable because of the fibers diameter, and matrix in situ properties, once the manufacturing process induces some issues like residual stresses and the generation of an interface. Alternatively, Tsai & Melo (2014) proposed the trace theory, where the trace of the plane stress stiffness matrix is used to define normalized relations with the lamina elastic properties. This theory is applicable just to CFRP and is also known as Tsai’s modulus (Arteiro et al., 2020).

This paper aims to extend this theory for GFRP. First, the asymptotic homogenization micromechanical model is applied considering a large range of usual glass fiber and polymeric matrix properties for unidirectional laminae. These properties are normalized by the trace and used as input for training the machine learning method named decision trees. Based on the decision trees results,

linear equations are obtained for the normalized properties. At last, the proposed equations are validated against experimental data compiled from the literature.

METHODOLOGY

The proposed methodology is defined in three steps. First, the asymptotic homogenization technique is briefly introduced. This micromechanical model is used to compute the lamina effective elastic properties using fiber and matrix properties as input. Next, the trace theory is discussed, where trace relations are defined using normalized material properties. This theory was proposed for CFRP, where the normalized properties are constants. For GFRP, a machine learning procedure is implemented using the decision trees to evaluate the relation between these normalized properties and the trace on the last part of the proposed approach.

Asymptotic Homogenization

The mathematical foundation of the asymptotic homogenization technique enables to establish a rigorous modeling approach for composite materials. The key point is that the displacement field can be defined assuming an asymptotical series in powers of ε and then strains are computed by kinematical relations and the stress using the constitutive equations.

Concerning the effective elastic properties of unidirectional laminae with square pattern symmetry, these solutions are usually obtained using infinite series to satisfy the boundary conditions. The analytical solution for isotropic fibers was first developed by Kalamkarov (1992) and later Castillero et al. (2012) proposed the following closed-form relations truncating the series

$$k = k_f V_f + k_m (1 - V_f) - \frac{V_f (k_m - k_f)^2 K}{m_m} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

$$l = l_f V_f + l_m (1 - V_f) - \frac{V_f (k_m - k_f) (l_m - l_f) K}{m_m} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

$$n = n_f V_f + n_m (1 - V_f) - \frac{V_f (k_m - k_f)^2 K}{m_m} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

$$p = p_m - 2V_f p_m P \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

$$m = m_m - V_f (m_m - m_f) M \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

$$m' = m_m - V_f (m_m - m_f) M' \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

where $k_{m,f} = E^{m,f} / [2(1 + \nu^{m,f})(1 - 2\nu^{m,f})]$, $p_{m,f} = m_{m,f} = E^{m,f} / [2(1 + \nu^{m,f})]$,

$n_{m,f} = [E^{m,f} (1 - \nu^{m,f})] / [(1 + \nu^{m,f})(1 - 2\nu^{m,f})]$, $l_{m,f} = (E^{m,f} \nu^{m,f}) / [(1 + \nu^{m,f})(1 - 2\nu^{m,f})]$, E^m is the matrix elastic modulus, ν^m is the matrix Poisson's ratio, E^f is the fiber elastic modulus and ν^f is the fiber Poisson's ratio. The following additional parameters are defined

$$K = C \left\{ V_m + \frac{29.7904(1 + \kappa_m)CR^8}{B^{-1} + R^6[AB^{-1}r + g + 29.7904DR^2]} \right\} \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

$$P = \frac{\chi_p}{(1 + V_f \chi_p - 29.7904 \chi_p^2 R^8)} \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

$$M = \frac{1 + \kappa_m}{[1 + \kappa_m (m_f / m_m)](1 + R^2 H^- - I)} \quad \text{Eq. 9}$$

$$M' = \frac{1 + \kappa_m}{[1 + \kappa_m (m_f / m_m)](1 + R^2 H^+ - I')} \quad \text{Eq. 10}$$

$$\kappa_{f,m} = 1 + 2(m_{f,m} / k_{f,m}) \quad \text{Eq. 11}$$

$$\chi_p = \frac{p_m - p_f}{p_m + p_f} \quad \text{Eq. 12}$$

$$H^+ = Ar_1 + Bk_m \pi + B(5.0153 + g_1) \quad \text{Eq. 13}$$

$$H^- = Ar_1 + Bk_m \pi - B(5.0153 + g_1) \quad \text{Eq. 14}$$

$$I = \frac{R^{12}(Ar_2 - Bg_2)(Ar_3 - Bg_3)}{1 + R^{10}(Ar_4 - Bg_4)} \quad \text{Eq. 15}$$

$$I' = \frac{R^{12}(Ar_2 + Bg_2)(Ar_3 + Bg_3)}{1 + R^{10}(Ar_4 + Bg_4)} \quad \text{Eq. 16}$$

$$A = \frac{[\kappa_m (m_f / m_m) - \kappa_f] B}{[(m_f / m_m) + \kappa_f]} \quad \text{Eq. 17}$$

$$B = \frac{[1 - (m_f / m_m)]}{[1 + \kappa_m (m_f / m_m)]} \quad \text{Eq. 18}$$

$$C = \frac{m_m}{[m_m + k_m V_f + k_f (1 - V_f)]} \quad \text{Eq. 19}$$

$$D = 2[(k_2 / k_1) - 1]C \quad \text{Eq. 20}$$

Additionally, $R = \sqrt{V_f / \pi}$, $r = 13312.0294R^{10}$, $r_1 = 29.7904R^6$, $r_2 = 281.6277R^6$, $r_3 = 1408.1385R^6$, $r_4 = 13312.0294R^6$, $g = -893.7124R^2 + 270.9309$, $g_1 = -18.9073R^2$, $g_2 = -119.1616R^2 + 27.0931$, $g_3 = -595.8082R^2 + 135.4655$ and $g_4 = -18197.4824R^2 + 4889.7209$. Note that these parameters do not have a clear physical meaning, they are obtained by Castillero et al. (2012) truncating the infinity series of the exact solution.

Using these equations, the lamina longitudinal elastic modulus, E_1 , transversal elastic modulus, E_2 , in-plane shear modulus, G_{12} , out-of-plane shear modulus, G_{23} , in-plane Poisson's ratio, ν_{12} , and the stiffness matrix, C , can be computed by

$$E_1 = \frac{nk - l^2}{k} \quad \text{Eq. 21}$$

$$E_2 = 4m' \left[\frac{nk - l^2}{n(k + m') - l^2} \right] \quad \text{Eq. 22}$$

$$G_{12} = p \quad \text{Eq. 23}$$

$$G_{23} = m' \quad \text{Eq. 24}$$

$$\nu_{12} = -\frac{l}{2k} \quad \text{Eq. 25}$$

$$C = \begin{bmatrix} 1/E_1 & -\nu_{12}/E_1 & -\nu_{12}/E_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\nu_{12}/E_1 & 1/E_2 & (2G_{23} - E_2)/2E_2G_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\nu_{12}/E_1 & (2G_{23} - E_2)/2E_2G_{23} & 1/E_2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/G_{23} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/G_{12} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/G_{12} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \quad \text{Eq. 26}$$

Trace Theory

Tsai & Melo (2014) claimed that the trace of stiffness matrix, $tr(C)$, can be assumed as a material property for a CFRP lamina and the normalized material properties are constants. On this basis, just one experimental test is required to characterize the lamina's elastic properties. Usually, E_1 is obtained experimentally in a simple uniaxial tensile test. This methodology has becoming popular in the literature due to its simplicity and good estimations (Arteiro et al., 2020; Tsai et al., 2022; Vignoli et al., 2022b).

The trace relation is defined by

$$tr(C) = \frac{E_1}{E_1^*} = \frac{E_2}{E_2^*} = \frac{G_{12}}{G_{12}^*} = \frac{G_{23}}{G_{23}^*} \quad \text{Eq. 27}$$

$$\nu_{12}^* = \nu_{12} \quad \text{Eq. 28}$$

where E_1^* , E_2^* , G_{12}^* , G_{23}^* and ν_{12}^* are the normalized properties.

For CFRP, these normalized properties can be assumed constant, but this hypothesis does not work very well for GFRP (Ha & Cimini Jr, 2018). To deal with this issue, a machine learning procedure is performed to evaluate these normalized properties.

Decision Trees

Decision Trees are very powerful Machine Learning algorithms capable of fitting complex datasets. They can perform both classification and regression tasks, and even multi output tasks (Geron, 2019). The goal of this algorithm is to create a model that predicts the value by learning simple decision rules inferred from the data features. This algorithm was chosen due to its advantages such as: it is simple to understand and to interpret, the trees can be visualised, it requires little data preparation and the computational cost is logarithmic in the number of data points used to train the tree (Pedregosa et al., 2011).

The machine learning process was written in Python and the libraries that were used are Scikit-Learn and Pandas. To begin the process it is necessary to divide the dataset into training and test sets, so the algorithm uses the train set to build the model and the test set is used to evaluate it. 80% of the examples in the dataset was used to build the training set and 20% to the test set as suggested in (Geron, 2019). After that, Scikit-Learn library is used to train and create the model. This library uses the Classification And Regression Tree (CART) algorithm.

As described by Pedregosa et al (2011), the algorithm first splits the training set in two subsets using a single feature k and a threshold tk . The algorithm searches for the pair (k, tk) that produces the purest subsets (weighted by their size). The cost function that the algorithm tries to minimize is given by Eq. 29.

$$J(k, t_k) = \frac{m_{left}}{m} G_{left} + \frac{m_{right}}{m} G_{right} \quad \text{Eq. 29}$$

where $G_{left/right}$ measure the impurity of the left/right subset and $m_{left/right}$ are the number of instances in the left/right subset.

Once it has successfully split the training set in two, it splits the subsets using the same logic, then the sub-subsets and so on, recursively. It stops recursing once it reaches the maximum depth or if it cannot find a split that will reduce impurity. The values used to for the hyperparameter of maximum depth were 5, 10 and 20. In order to choose the best value of this hyperparameter we applied the K-fold cross-validation. This technique randomly splits the training set into k distinct subsets called folds, then it trains and evaluates the Decision Tree model k times, picking a different fold for evaluation every time and training on the other $(k-1)$ folds. The result is an array containing the k evaluation scores and obtained the best value to create the final model. The value of K that was used is 10 and the best value for the hyperparameter maximum depth obtained is 5.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section is split into two parts: first, the results of the proposed methodology are introduced to obtain the explicit trace relations and next the estimations of these equations are compared with a set of experimental data compiled from the literature.

Figure 1: Generated data using asymptotic homogenization for: (a) E_1^* ; (b) E_2^* ; (c) G_{12}^* ; (d) G_{23}^* ; and (e) ν_{12}^* . The color bars indicate the frequency.

Figure 1 shows the data generated using the asymptotic homogenization method, where the color bar represents the frequency of each normalized property according to the trace. The constituents' ranges considered to generate the data are: $3\text{GPa} \leq E^m \leq 5\text{GPa}$, $0.3 \leq \nu^m \leq 0.4$, $70\text{GPa} \leq E^f \leq 90\text{GPa}$, $0.2 \leq \nu^f \leq 0.3$ and $0.3 \leq V_f \leq 0.7$. Each of these constituents properties ranges are split into 9 equally spaced divisions, resulting 59049 combinations. In other words, the properties of 59049 laminae are computed using the asymptotic homogenization to generate training data. Note that this amount of experimental data is not available, what makes the asymptotic homogenization micromechanical model an essential tool for the proposed approach.

Figure 2 introduces the decision trees results after the machine learning training (pink circles) and the linear equations proposed (black lines). A good agreement can be realized for the points with the highest frequency. It is important to highlight that a linear equation type is selected based on the decision trees results.

Figure 2: Decision tree points (pink) and fit linear relations (black) for: (a) E_1^* ; (b) E_2^* ; (c) G_{12}^* ; (d) G_{23}^* ; and (e) ν_{12}^* .

To validate the equations proposed in Fig. 2, 10 laminae with the five independent elastic properties measured experimentally are selected from the literature (Barbero, 2018; Bledzki et al., 1999; Chen et al., 2022; Gibson, 2012; Gudmundson & Zang, 1993; Gusev et al., 2000; Kaddour & Hinton, 2012; Ladhwe et al., 2014; Soden et al., 1998). The experimental laminae properties are listed in Table 1. Using the laminae properties, the trace and the normalized properties are computed.

Table 1: Experimental data compiled from the literature

Reference	Laminae	E_1 [GPa]	E_2 [GPa]	G_{12} [GPa]	G_{23} [GPa]	ν_{12}	$tr(C)$ [GPa]
Soden et al. (1998)	1	53.48	17.7	5.83	6.32	0.278	139.3
Soden et al. (1998)	2	45.6	16.2	5.83	5.79	0.278	126.4
Bledzki et al. (1999)	3	38.84	12.12	5.09	4.78	0.255	98.1
Gibson (2012)	4	31.0	7.48	2.84	2.58	0.320	70.7
Kaddour & Hinton (2012)	5	52.0	19.0	6.7	6.7	0.300	149.0
Gusev et al. (2000)	6	41.5	17.1	5.63	6.07	0.316	128.6
Chen et al. (2021)	7	52.4	15.95	4.57	5.62	0.310	129.6
Ladhwe et al. (2015)	8	39.47	12.97	3.89	4.63	0.276	100.8
Gudmundson & Zang (1993)	9	41.7	13.0	3.4	4.58	0.300	102.9
Barbero (2018)	10	37.9	11.3	3.3	3.9	0.300	93.6

The normalized properties from experimental data and estimated using the proposed analytical equations are presented in Table 2 and in Fig. 3. The average errors are 4.63% for E_1^* , 4.58% for E_2^* , 10.40% for G_{12}^* , 11.58% for G_{23}^* and 5.88% for ν_{12}^* .

Table 2: Normalized laminae properties

Laminae	E_1^*		E_2^*		G_{12}^*		G_{23}^*		ν_{12}^*	
	exp	ana	exp	ana	exp	ana	exp	ana	exp	ana
1	0.384	0.369	0.127	0.137	0.0418	0.0423	0.0454	0.0535	0.278	0.285
2	0.361	0.381	0.128	0.133	0.0461	0.0415	0.0458	0.0512	0.278	0.289
3	0.396	0.406	0.124	0.124	0.0519	0.0398	0.0487	0.0462	0.255	0.297
4	0.439	0.431	0.106	0.115	0.0402	0.0382	0.0365	0.0414	0.320	0.305
5	0.349	0.361	0.128	0.140	0.0450	0.0428	0.0450	0.0552	0.300	0.282
6	0.323	0.379	0.133	0.134	0.0438	0.0416	0.0472	0.0516	0.316	0.288
7	0.405	0.378	0.123	0.134	0.0353	0.0417	0.0434	0.0518	0.310	0.288
8	0.392	0.404	0.129	0.125	0.0386	0.0400	0.0459	0.0467	0.276	0.296
9	0.405	0.402	0.126	0.126	0.0330	0.0400	0.0445	0.0471	0.300	0.296
10	0.405	0.410	0.121	0.122	0.0352	0.0395	0.0417	0.0454	0.300	0.298

Figure 3: Comparison between the proposed trace relations for the normalized properties and the experimental data.

These average errors indicate that the proposed equations have great estimations compared with different micromechanical models reported by Vignoli et al. (2019), Vignoli et al. (2021) and Vignoli et al. (2022a). Nevertheless, the constituents properties are not required, avoiding issues related to the uncertainties of fiber and matrix in situ properties. Once the linear equations for the normalized properties are obtained combining asymptotic homogenization and decision trees, just one macromechanical elastic property is necessary to completely characterize the 3D elastic properties, all the other properties can be obtained using the trace relation. The simplest case is to obtain E_1 experimentally in an uniaxial tensile test. If E_1 is known, the $tr(C)$ can be computed using the equation for E_1^* and all the other properties are also obtained.

The original trace theory proposed by Tsai & Melo (2014) is valid just for CFRP and the normalized properties are constants, instead of linear equations proposed in this study. Ha & Cimini Jr (2018) demonstrated that if the normalized properties are constants, the error for GFRP is considerably higher and the trace theory cannot be applied. However, with the proposed modification, a simple set of equations can be used with a great reliability for GFRP.

CONCLUSIONS

The present investigation applies the asymptotic homogenization micromechanical model combined with the decision trees algorithm to obtain a simple set of linear equations for GFRP unidirectional lamina properties using the concept of trace theory, where the elastic properties are normalized by the trace of the stiffness matrix. The results indicate that the average error of the normalized relations compared with experimental data are very small. In summary, just one elastic properties need to be measured experimentally, decreasing the requirement of tests, which implies that the cost and time to design GFRP structures also decrease significantly.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

All necessary data is presented in this paper.

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